

Income tax reform in the Philippines — A comparative analysis of its impact for micro, small and medium enterprises amidst the pandemic

Lorille J. Leones*

Accountancy Department, School of Business and Computer Studies, St. Dominic College of Asia,
Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines

*Corresponding author: ljleones@sdca.edu.ph

Abstract

The pandemic brought a significant change to different business industries around the world. One of the most affected sectors in this crisis is micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs). Due to the risk of spreading the virus within the workplace and the limited number of customers, these businesses were forced to temporarily cease their operations. Having limited resources, such as working capital, the prolonged closure of its operation brought serious financial losses, resulting in temporary closures, the retrenchment of employees, and a decrease in their productivity. Companies had to open up their reserved funds to continuously operate despite the pandemic. Other arrangements were also made to minimize the risk of exposing the workers to the virus. Several measures were implemented to support MSMEs and help them bounce back to their active operations. The recent enactment of tax reform is one of the measures expected to help small businesses lessen the negative impact of the pandemic. It provides for lower tax rates and higher tax exemptions for different sectors. Although it is expected that the tax relief will lessen the source of government revenue, this tax reform aims to offset the loss by increasing investments, employment, and active business operations. This study aims to analyze the impact of the tax reform on small establishments in the midst of the crisis. The salient provisions of the reform programs will be compared to the previous tax laws and will be applied to the data gathered. With the information collected, the study will provide a better understanding of the effects of tax reform on the financial performance of MSMEs.

Keywords: Micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs); Pandemic; Tax reform.

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Introduction

Micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) significantly contribute to the national economy in terms of revenue generation and job creation for most Filipino workers. An MSME in the Philippines is defined as any business activity or enterprise engaged in industry, agribusiness, and/or services that has: (1) an asset size, excluding land, of up to P100 million; and (2) an employment size of less than 200 employees (Senate Economic Planning Office, 2012). According to the 2019 Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) report, there are 995,745 MSMEs in the Philippines, representing 99.5% of the total business enterprises in the country. With this significant number of businesses, MSMEs contributed the largest portion to the country's overall employment, generating 62.4% of the total labor workforce (Philippine Commission on Women, 2020).

Due to the COVID-19 outbreak and the implementation of the strictest community quarantine in the first quarter of 2020, a rapid decrease in the number of operating businesses led to a decrease in overall employment and revenue contribution to the government treasury. In the study conducted by an Asian Development Bank's senior economist, an average of 70% of the total MSMEs in the country decided to

temporarily close their businesses during the enhanced community quarantine period (Shinozaki & Rao, 2020).

Generally, the main purpose of establishing a business is to generate profit. Due to the virus outbreak, several businesses had to adopt various measures to lessen, if not prevent, the losses suffered during their operations. The government implemented rules that businesses must follow in applying mitigating loss measures, such as retrenchment programs. In managing internal operations, businesses must utilize cost-cutting measures such as reduction of non-essential expenses and adoption of different working hours schemes (Guliman & Uy, 2019).

Despite these countermeasures to lessen the losses, the number of shut-down businesses continues to increase. With this, the government proposed and subsequently enacted laws to reform the taxation rules in the country. It is expected that this implementation will help individual taxpayers and businesses recover from the negative impact of the pandemic on the industry.

Literature Review

Status of MSMEs during the Pandemic

The working capital shortage forced MSMEs to either temporarily close their businesses or perpetually cease their operations while the community quarantine subsisted in the country. In a survey conducted by the International Labour Organization (ILO) in May 2020, the following effects of the pandemic on MSMEs were noted: First, 75% of MSMEs are experiencing a decrease in revenue or income. The prohibition to operate of some businesses due to the risk of spreading the virus brought rapid depletion on their working capital. Second, 50% of MSMEs experienced a gradual drop in their product or service demand or order. Such a decrease is connected to the financial performance of the business. Third, the labor workforce is significantly affected. Seven out of ten companies have to reduce their production capacity because of cost-cutting measures such as retrenchment programs (International Labour Organization, 2020). The most alarming condition of the labor workforce is when low-income earners have to lose their jobs or take forced leave without any pay at their companies.

Among the neighboring countries, the Philippines has the highest number of temporarily closed businesses two months after the start of lockdown. 70.6% of the MSMEs had to cease operations; this was followed by Lao People's Democratic Republic with 61.1%, Indonesia with 48.6%, and Thailand with 41.1%. To cope with the negative effects of the pandemic, some businesses would rely on credit access, such as bank loans, to fund their operations. In a study conducted by the ADB in October 2020, aside from credit access, business subsidies and tax relief are the most desired measures by MSMEs. From March to April 2020, 73.3% of the respondents expressed their strong desire to avail of tax reliefs from the government. This measure is followed by the desire to receive subsidies for business recovery, cash transfers, and grants that will help in its continuous operation. There are other measures that small businesses would like to avail of during the pandemic. This includes assistance to pay for their employees' salaries, teleworking arrangements, deferred utility payments, simplified or eased requirements for public procurement, one-stop service windows to support MSME exporters and importers, and other support (Asian Development Bank, 2020). Among these measures, the most important ones that MSMEs would like to avail of are financial subsidies and tax relief from the government (Shinozaki, 2020).

Incentive and Negative Effects of Tax Reform to the Economy

Tax reform has its own positive and negative impact on the economy. Generally, if the focus of the reform is to lower taxes for those who belong to the poverty line, the tax rate for middle- and higher-income earners will increase to balance the effect of such changes. The impact of a tax reform depends on its main objective. If the amendments focus on simplifying the tax system and reducing the tax obligations of

citizens, it will decrease the overall revenue collection of the government. Taxes are the lifeblood of the government. Without it, the government will not be able to operate. That is why, when the tax collections of the government decrease, it will also decrease its reserved funds. Tax cuts can slow economic development due to the continuous increase in deficits. The government will rely on foreign loans to finance its projects and other activities (Tax Policy Center, 2020). Such a deficit will also raise interest rates. Despite this impact, in the long run, it is expected that tax reform programs will result in an increase in the number of investments, local or foreign. The opening of more businesses will also open more job opportunities for its people and reduce the poverty rate.

Tax relief would also increase the demand for production. Such a decrease will result in an increase in the disposable income of a family. The higher the after-tax incomes, households would spend more, increasing the demand for goods and services. Also, with the decrease in tax obligations, more businesses will be able to save or allocate funds for investments. Such expansion would lessen the unemployment rate and poverty rate in the country (Page et al., 2017).

Tax reform has both positive and negative effects on the economy. It is important that the legislature ensure that, in the structure of the reform program, the beneficial effect must outweigh its deficit effect in the long run. Not all tax changes will have the same impact on growth. It may have auspicious effects on the long-term size of the economy but may also create trade-offs between equity and efficiency (Gale & Samwick, 2017).

Tax Reform in the Philippines

The prevailing tax law in the Philippines is the National Internal Revenue Code (NIRC). This law was amended by Republic Act 8424, or “*The Tax Reform Act of 1997*,” on January 1, 1998. This codifies the rules for the national taxation system in the country. With the goal of spurring economic growth, creating jobs, and encouraging investments, several tax reform packages were proposed and enacted by the government over the past few years. On December 19, 2017, R.A. 10963, or the Tax Reform for Acceleration and Inclusion (TRAIN) Law, was passed into law. The salient provisions of this law are to lower and simplify personal income taxes, estate and donor taxes, an expanded value-added tax base, and adjustments to excise taxes. It also introduced the government’s Tax Amnesty Program to encourage errant taxpayers to settle their outstanding tax liabilities and properly settle their legal interests. The most recent tax reform package is R.A. 11534, or the Corporate Recovery and Tax Incentives for Enterprises Act (CREATE), which was passed into law on March 26, 2021. The salient provision of the law is to reduce corporate tax rates and encourage investments in the country. It will also help businesses that suffered great losses in their operations during the pandemic.

The following table differentiates the salient provisions between the tax laws prior to and after the implementation of tax reform programs.

Table 1. Comparison of the salient provisions amended by the tax reform programs

	Comprehensive Tax Reform Programs				
	1997 NIRC		TRAIN (RA 10963)		CREATE (RA 11534)
Taxable income and tax rates for individual and corporate taxpayers	Individual Taxpayers: Income tax is computed based on the following graduated income tax schedule:		Individual Taxpayers: R.A. 10963 revised the graduated income tax schedule effective January 1, 2018, to December 31, 2022		Corporate Taxpayers: Under the R.A 11534, tax rate for a domestic corporation, in general, is fixed at 25% effective July 1, 2020. Starting 2022, tax rate shall be reduced by
	Not over P10,000	5%	Not over P250,000	0%	

Over P10,000 but not over P30,000	P500+10% of the excess over P10,000	Over P250,000 but not over P400,000	20% of the excess over P250,000	1% annually until year 2027. For corporations, whose net taxable income is less than P5 million during the taxable year and total assets not exceeding P100 million, excluding land on which the business is situated, the corporate tax rate is fixed at 20%. The minimum corporate income tax is lowered to 1%.
Over P30,000 but not over P70,000	P2,500+15% of the excess over P30,000	Over P400,000 but not over P800,000	P30,000 + 25% of the excess over P400,000	
Over P70,000 but not over P140,000	P8,500+20% of the excess over P70,000	Over P800,000 but not over P2,000,000	P130,000 + 30% of the excess over P800,000	
Over P140,000 but not over P250,000	P22,500+25% of the excess over P140,000	Over P2,000,000 but not over P8,000,000	P490,000 + 32% of the excess over P2,000,000	
Over P250,000 but not over P500,000	P50,000+30% of the excess over P250,000	Over P8,000,000	P2,410,000 + 35% of the excess over P8,000,000	
Over P500,000	P125,000+32% of the excess over P500,000	Tax schedule effective January 1, 2023, and onwards:		

<p>Corporate Taxpayers:</p> <p>Domestic corporations, in general is taxed at a fixed rate of 30% of the net taxable income.</p> <p>The minimum corporate income tax is set as 2% of the corporate gross income.</p>	Not over P250,000	0%
	Over P250,000 but not over P400,000	15% of the excess over P250,000
	Over P400,000 but not over P800,000	P22,500 + 20% of the excess over P400,000
	Over P800,000 but not over P2,000,000	P102,500 + 25% of the excess over P800,000
	Over P2,000,000 but not over P8,000,000	P402,500 + 30% of the excess over P2,000,000
	Over P8,000,000	P2,202,500 + 35% of the excess over P8,000,000

Tax exemptions	All individual taxpayers engaged in trade or business, practice of professions and	Basic and additional personal exemptions are removed under the TRAIN law. All individual	Not applicable for corporations.
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	<p>earning compensation income is entitled for a basic personal exemption of P50,000.</p> <p>For every qualified dependent, the taxpayer is entitled to an additional personal exemption of P25,000 but limited to a maximum of four (4) dependents.</p>	<p>taxpayers are entitled to a fixed tax exemption of P250,000.</p>	
<p>Income tax for purely self-employed individuals and/or professionals</p>	<p>Net taxable income of individual is subject to the graduated income tax table under the 1997 NIRC and gross income is subject to percentage tax.</p>	<p>An option to be taxed at 8% of the gross sales/receipts and other income less the P250,000 tax exemption for every individual taxpayer. The 8% income tax shall be in lieu of the graduated income tax rates.</p> <p>However, if the gross sales/receipts or other income exceeds the VAT threshold of P3 million, it shall be tax based on the graduated income tax rate.</p>	<p>Income tax for purely self-employed individuals and/or professionals</p>

Sources: 1997 National Internal Revenue Code, Republic Act 10963 or Tax Reform for Acceleration and Inclusion (TRAIN) and Republic Act 11534 or Corporate Recovery and Tax Incentives for Enterprises (CREATE) Act

Methodology

The study used an exploratory and quantitative research method that uses numerical data and reports to investigate the negative effects of the pandemic on MSMEs as well as the advantages and disadvantages of the implementation of tax reform packages. Data were collected from the latest available statistical reports of government agencies such as, but not limited to, the Philippine Statistics Authority, the Department of Finance, and the Department of Trade and Industry. From this data, sample computations were made in accordance with the rules provided by the tax reform laws. Inferences were made from the collected numerical data and the results of the estimated computations.

Results and Discussion

Comparison of Income Taxes Paid by MSME after the Tax Reform

Businesses contribute their share to the government through the payment of taxes. Through this contribution, the funding requirements for various government projects were supported. With the implementation of the tax reform programs, some sectors were able to benefit from the decrease in their obligations. However, for some other sectors, their taxes are much higher compared to the previous rules due to the increase in tax rates.

To show an example of the difference between the taxes paid by a business before and after the tax reform, data gathered from the 2018 Census of the Philippine Business and Industry (CPBI) was used for the computation. The figure below shows the total revenue and expenses incurred by businesses engaged in accommodation and food service activities for one whole year.

Figure 1. Total Revenue and Expense for Accommodation and Food Service Activities by Industry Group, Philippines: 2018 CPBI

Based on the report, there are 44,487 food establishments in the country in 2018. (PSA, Census of Philippine Business and Industry: Accommodation and Food Service Activities, 2018) Using the averaging method, the net income of a business and taxes prior to and after the tax reforms are as follows.

Prior to the Amendments in the 1997 NIRC:

Revenue	18,904,399.00
Expense	16,317,126.00
Net income	2,587,272.00
Income tax due of an individual taxpayer availing the maximum personal exemptions	744,927.04
Income tax due if the business is a corporate taxpayer	776,181.00

Upon the Effectivity of TRAIN and CREATE laws:

Revenue	18,904,399.00
Expense	16,317,126.00
Net income	2,587,272.00
Income tax due if the business is an individual taxpayer using the graduated income tax schedule	677,927.04
Income tax due if the business is a corporate taxpayer	646,818.00

With the implementation of the tax reforms, an average sole proprietor earning a net income of around P2.5 million will be able to save P70,000 for taxes annually. Also, a corporation earning the same net income will be able to save an average of P130,000 per year. Assuming that this will be the average

savings of each taxpayer, businesses in this industry will be able to save around P5.8 billion in a year. This only pertains to the accommodation and food industries.

The current VAT threshold in the latest tax rules is P3 million. Generally, MSME generates revenue of less than P3 million per taxable year. Assuming that this will be the basis of computation, the following will show the comparison of income taxes paid prior to and after the tax reform.

Prior to the Amendments in the 1997 NIRC:

Revenue	3,000,000.00
Expense	1,200,000.00
Gross income	1,800,000.00
Income tax due of an individual taxpayer	493,000.00
Percentage tax (3%)	90,000.00

Upon the Effectivity of TRAIN and CREATE laws:

Revenue	3,000,000.00
Expense	1,200,000.00
Gross income	1,800,000.00
Income tax due of an individual taxpayer using the graduated income tax schedule	39,000.00
Percentage tax (3%)	90,000.00
Income tax due of an individual taxpayer using the 8% flat rate	124,000.00

Individual taxpayers whose gross annual revenue is equal to or less than P3 million per year may avail themselves of either the graduated income tax schedule or an 8% flat rate in the computation of income taxes. If the taxpayer opted to use the graduated income tax schedule, either using the itemized deduction or the optional standard deduction, he or she is still required to pay percentage tax based on his gross revenue. On the other hand, if the taxpayer opted to use the 8% flat rate, it would be in lieu of all other taxes.

In summary, using the sample data above, an individual taxpayer below the standard threshold will pay P583,000 annually for the taxes. After the tax reform, the taxpayer will only pay either P129,000 using graduated income tax or P124,000 using the 8% flat rate. This will result in an average annual tax savings of P364,000 for micro, small, and medium enterprises.

Using the latest number of MSMEs provided in the 2019 PSA Report, if there are 995,745 establishments in the country, an average savings of P364,000 will generate a consolidated tax savings of around P365 billion annually for small businesses. It can be inferred from the above results that businesses with smaller revenue and net income generate more tax savings compared to those large entities with higher revenues and net income. Though the tax rates for low-income earners decreased with the implementation of tax reforms, the tax rates for those earning higher incomes did not decrease significantly.

Conclusion

The implementation of the tax reform programs contributed to the savings of small businesses during the pandemic. It is more favorable to those who are low-income taxpayers in the country. When the TRAIN law was enacted, individual taxpayers were able to reduce their tax obligations to the government. This resulted in higher take-home pay for employees and sole proprietors. Also, with the enactment of the CREATE Act, corporate taxpayers are expected to save more funds due to the gradual decrease in tax rates. Through this, business expenses will decrease, which will assist MSMEs in coping with the negative impact

of the pandemic. Some amendments are effective only for a certain period of time. An example is the imposition of a minimum corporate income tax. The lowered tax rate will help most small businesses until June 2023. This limitation assumes that businesses will be able to bounce back to their active operations two years from now. Once the original tax rate is reapplied, businesses will have to pay again for higher taxes. It is understandable that the government indeed relies on taxes for its operation. The lower the tax collections, the fewer the public projects. However, if the decrease in the revenue of the government will offset the increase in the labor workforce, more businesses, and new investments due to lower taxes, it would be a better policy to maintain the lower tax rates as long as they are sustainable for the economy. The evaluation of the tax reforms will only be determined once the overall impact of lowered tax rates is available a few years from now. During this pandemic, the burden on small businesses to shoulder high expenses but low revenue will be minimized with the imposition of lower taxes. Certainly, this is one of the supports that MSME needs from the government amidst the global crisis.

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